

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 10; October 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

It is a great pleasure to see this special issue on the "Classroom of the Future". I would like to thank the editor Patricia A. Carlson for her excellent work, and the authors for their invaluable contributions. Hope all readers will enjoy this issue!

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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